

THE IMPACT OF AI GENERATED CONTENT TO INCREASE CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT ON SOCIAL MEDIA

SANNAS SALSABILA R¹, NILO LEGOWO²

¹ Information Systems Management Department, Binus Graduate Program, Master of Management Information Systems, Bina Nusantara University, Jakarta, Indonesia 1148

² Information Systems Management Department, Binus Graduate Program, Master of Management Information Systems, Bina Nusantara University, Jakarta, Indonesia 11480

E-mail: ¹ sannas.salsabila@binus.ac.id, ² nlegowo@binus.edu

ABSTRACT

The use of social media now plays a crucial role for companies in interacting with customers. However, less than 50% of businesses have successfully utilized it effectively. The main issue is that the content is uninteresting and irrelevant, leading to a decreased in customer engagement. Therefore, this research aims to determine whether AI-Generated Content can enhance customer engagement on social media. This research was conducted by distributing questionnaires to residents of DKI Jakarta, Indonesia, who have purchased products marketed through social media (TikTok and Instagram), where the content generated was AI Generated Content. In this study, a total of 494 respondents were collected. This research conduct using the customer engagement in social media framework (CESM) combined with several other variables that support studies on customer engagement. This study demonstrates that AI-Generated Content (AIGC) significantly enhances customer engagement on social media. Increased social interaction and hedonic motivation effectively address challenges on social media by generating content quickly while maintaining visually appealing quality. Additionally, the improvement in satisfaction, influenced by increased commitment and trust, can trigger active customer interactions, ultimately boosting customer engagement. Meanwhile, positive emotion has a relatively lower impact, as customer responses to AIGC's ability to provide relaxation and humor are often not very strong. Based on the research findings, it is hoped that business owners can address various issues that arise during the marketing process by understanding the potential and limitations in the creation of AI-generated content.

Keywords: *AI-Generated Content, Social Media, Customer Engagement, Customer Interaction, AI Content*

1. INTRODUCTION

In the digital era, social media has evolved from a communication tool into a key marketing platform. Platforms like TikTok and Instagram help brands boost awareness (69%) and website traffic (52%) [1]. Social media is essential for businesses, with 77% using it to maintain customer connections and 41% of small business owners relying on it for revenue [2]. Despite its importance, many businesses struggle with effective social media marketing. Research shows that over 50% of companies fail to utilize it successfully [3].

A December 2024 survey of 118 Jakarta residents found that 60.2% were not engaged with the content displayed on social media. The causes of low customer engagement with social media content are outlined in table 1 below.

Table 1: Causes of Low Customer Engagement with Social Media Content

No	Reason	Percentage
1	Unappealing content	29%
2	Irrelevant content	21%

3	Monotonous or non-varied content	17%
4	Ambiguous or insufficient information	13%
5	Fails to follow current trends	8%
6	Others	13%

Based on tabel 1, it can be seen that the cause of low customer engagement on social media are unappealing content, both in terms of visuals and suboptimal editing quality, which accounts for 29% of the cases. Following this, 21% of customers find the content irrelevant to their interests and needs. Additionally, 17% of engagement issues arise due to monotonous or non-varied content ideas and overly frequent repetition of theme. Ambiguous or insufficient information is another factor, contributing to 13% of low engagement. Furthermore, 8% of cases are caused by content that fails to follow current trends. Lastly, other unspecified reasons make up the remaining 13%,

Other research shows that the failure of social media marketing is often due to irrelevant and unappealing content [4]. Key challenges include difficulties in creating engaging content, maintaining consistency, differentiation, and quality, as well as aligning content with internal and external needs [5], [6]. These obstacles reduce customer engagement on social media. A survey also found that brands struggle to build engagement due to a lack of relevance and authenticity in their content [7]. The decrease in engagement can be seen by survey conducted by haws in 2020 [8], which shows a decline in interactions on social media platforms TikTok and Instagram.

The decreased in engagement is evident in social media trends. By late 2023, Instagram saw a 50% drop in interactions compared to early 2022, while TikTok experienced a 39% decreased. Video marketing has also suffered, with views on Instagram decreasing by 49% and on TikTok by 26%. This decreased is due to brands producing less engaging content. Engagement on TikTok dropped by 35% in the past year, while Instagram saw a 25–45% decrease across different post types, including photos, carousels, reels, and videos [8].

This decreased engagement negatively impacts businesses by reducing purchase intent, brand loyalty, and trust [9], [10], [11]. It can also lead to lower shareholder value and revenue [12]. To counteract these effects, many businesses are adopting AI-generated content (AIGC). A December 2024 survey of 118 Jakarta residents found that AI was used most for content creation on TikTok (75.4%), followed by Instagram (59.3%). AI systems mimic human intelligence by learning, planning, and processing information, enabling them to generate high-quality content efficiently [13].

A 2023 McKinsey survey found that 22% of professionals across industries use AI regularly, with 14% applying it in marketing and sales for content creation. AI is reshaping social media by automating content production, including text, images, and videos, improving efficiency and engagement [14]. Research highlights AI's role in copywriting (76%), creative inspiration (71%), market analysis (63%), and image generation (62%) [15]. AI allows businesses to stay ahead of trends while maintaining engagement at lower costs [16].

AIGC able to enhances brand performance, creativity, and cost efficiency, proving valuable in digital marketing [17]. Studies emphasize its role in

language localization and its positive influence on brand awareness, loyalty, and purchase intent [14]. AIGC is considered revolutionary across industries [18], particularly in marketing and service delivery. By analyzing user behavior, AI-generated content fosters higher engagement [18]. The way content is presented impacts user interaction, where engaging content strengthens relationships, while dissatisfaction leads to disengagement [19].

According to previous study, the use of AIGC has a considerable appeal, showing an impact comparable with the use of human influencer [20]. Besides that, with the ability to produce diverse style and formats make AIGC able to offers business owners divers content to enhance customer engagement. As a result, 49% of business owners started that content created by AI performs better than content made by humans [21] other survey states that 56% of respondents prefer AIGC over manually generated content and 55% respondents aged 16-24 are more engage with AIGC compare to human generated content [22]. This condition demonstrates the significant potential of AIGC. However, this positive response contrast with other studies that state if AIGC is often perceived as lacking authenticity and credibility that tend to lower engagement [23].

Despite these advantages, concerns remain about AIGC's potential risks, such as factual inaccuracies [14] and ethical issues regarding user data privacy. Highly personalized AI-generated content raises questions about data collection and consent [24]. Ensure alignment between the content with the brand and customer also an important concern, which could undermine brand credibility. Research on customer engagement is essential, as it fosters loyalty, emotional connections, and long-term brand relationships [25].

It is imperative to comprehend the relevance of this issue to research, as diminished customer engagement has the capacity to exert an influence on the effectiveness of marketing content, in addition to its impact on customer loyalty, purchase intent, and overall company revenue [9], [10]. Despite the growing global use of artificial intelligence (AI) in content creation, there remains a gap in the existing literature regarding how AI-generated content (AIGC) contributes to relationship building and customer engagement, as well as the impact of technological, social, and motivational factors on this engagement [9], [26]. Particularly within a local context such as Indonesia, which is

characterised by its distinctive user demographics. In order to address these issues, the present study employs a variables based on a combination of previous studies. This study elucidates the contemporary phenomenon and employs an empirical approach to evaluate the efficacy of AIGC as a contemporary solution in the realm of digital marketing.

Although the utilization of social media has become a customary component of digital marketing strategies, the inadequate level of customer engagement indicates that a social media presence alone is insufficient to ensure marketing success. This issue remains salient, as customer engagement exerts an influence not only on the short-term relationship between brands and customers, but also on loyalty, purchase intent, and overall business performance [9], [10]. In this context, the utilization of AI Generated Content (AIGC) is becoming increasingly significant, yet it has not been the subject of extensive in-depth discussion in relation to its effectiveness on engagement. Consequently, a comprehensive conceptual understanding and theoretical approach is required to examine how factors such as trust, commitment, and information quality mediated by positive emotion and satisfaction toward AIGC able to influence customer engagement. Consequently, it is anticipated that this research will be able to make theoretical and practical contributions to the resolution of contemporary problems faced by many business people in today's digital era.

Therefore, this study aims to examine whether AI-Generated Content can address existing challenges and enhance customer engagement on social media, particularly on TikTok and Instagram, which have experienced a decreased in customer engagement. This research will be structured based on models from previous studies in formulating variables to improve customer engagement on social media. This study seeks to answer two research questions: (1.) What factors influence the use of AI-Generated Content on social media in relation to customer engagement? (2) To what extent do these factors affect the use of AI-Generated Content on social media in relation to customer engagement? The research through this approach expected to provide new insights into the AI-generated content potential and limitations, particularly in understanding the connection among customers and brands through AI-generated content on social media.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Social Media

Social media remains a digital platform which promotes networking and information sharing [27], having an essential role to influence public opinion and decision-making [28]. Social media in the context of AI is essential to communicate and share AI-generated content with the public ([29], [30]). Social media transformed interactions between brands and consumers [27]; social media helps attract, retain, and interact with customers, which is crucial to fostering strong brand relationships [11]. Strong social media engagement is a crucial customer loyalty and brand influence indicator. By leveraging social media effectively, a brand can strengthen customer relationships, enhance brand visibility, and gain sustained customer involvement and royalty [31].

2.2 Artificial Intelligence Generated Content

Generative AI (GenAI) is an AI subset focused to create diverse content, such as text, images, video, audio, and 3D models [29], [32]. It leverages natural language processing (NLP) to comprehend and construct human language and natural language generation (NLG) to generate text-based result. Through the analysis patterns in data, GenAI creates realistic and complex content that imitates human-generated material [16]. AI-Generated Content (AIGC) can generate product descriptions, edit images, and create short videos using user-inputted terms [14], [18], [33]. The implementation in media and marketing enhances customer engagement as a virtual assistant [34], establishing AIGC as an essential tool for modern marketing efforts [33].

2.3 Research Variables

The selection of models and variables in this study is based on a combination of previous studies, where have proven relevant in measuring customer engagement on social media which is in accordance with the topic in this study. The use of the CESM model has shown how trust, commitment, positive emotion, and satisfaction can shape customer engagement on social media [9]. While, the other model develops more comprehensive factors by adding social, technological, and motivational factors. Based on previous theoretical frameworks, this research will combine several

variables to measure customer engagement [26]. In this study, there will be eight variables:

2.1.1 Commitment

Commitment shows customers' willingness to remain in a sustainable relationship, develop brand community interactions, and support the brand. [9]. In the social media marketing context, commitment is a psychological condition that drives individuals to take specific actions, like connection with a brand [11].

2.1.2 Trust

Trust in technology allows people to believe in expected outcomes [35]. In social media, trust shows user confidence in integrity, reliability, and data security platform. It gives consumer attitudes and influences engagement, whether positive or negative. High trust degrades concerns about privacy and security [36], developing active participation and engaging customer engagement.

2.1.3 Information Quality

Information quality shows the effectiveness in content satisfies customer needs and conveys intended messages [37], [38]. Information quality on social media is an aspect like relevance, competence, accuracy, and usefulness that become key to measures of satisfaction. Ensuring high information quality helps gauge customer engagement [39].

2.1.4 Hedonic Motivation

Hedonic motivation relating to customers emotional needs, such as pleasure, enjoyment, and happiness [26]. The connection between hedonic motivation and AI utilization is assessed with AI generates enhanced pleasure and excitement, which can drive greater engagement [40]. Then, the hedonic motivation influence on customer engagement observed in the desire to engage in pleasurable behavior [41].

2.1.5 Positive Emotion

Positive emotions include feelings of enthusiasm, freedom of expression, and the

anticipation of favorable outcomes. These emotions reflect a mental state shaped by cognitive and affective assessments of consumption experiences. They are believed to influence mindsets that drive behaviors such as hedonic values and customer engagement [9].

2.1.6 Positive Emotion

Satisfaction is essential for customer engagement on social media, influencing connection, interaction, loyalty, and advocacy [19]. In social media satisfaction shaped by how well their needs and expectations are met. High satisfaction often correlates with loyalty [36].

2.1.7 Social Interaction

Social interaction refers to the interactions among customers with goals to fulfil their satisfaction and needs [26]. Social media transforms traditional interactions into interactive dialogues, where these interactions become knowledge sources that help brand achieve customer engagement more easily, forming the primary process in building relationship networks [19], [42].

2.1.8 Customer Engagement

Customer engagement refers to customer interactions with a company's content, products, or services on social media, influencing marketing outcomes and relationships [43]. It involves active participation, such as clicking, liking, sharing, and commenting [36].

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Statement of Research Variable

In this study, there are eight variables used by the author, which are commitment, trust, information quality, hedonic motivation, positive emotion, user satisfaction, social interaction, and customer engagement, which later will be distributed to respondents in the form of a survey as seen on table 2.

Table 2: Statement of Research Variable

Variables	Indicators		Sources
Commitment	CM1	I am willing to maintain a long-term relationship with brands that use AI-generated content on social media (Instagram and TikTok).	[44]
	CM2	I will continue to interact with brands that use AI-generated content in social media marketing (Instagram and TikTok).	[9]
	CM3	I feel a connection with brands that create marketing content using AI on social media (Instagram and TikTok)	[11]
	CM4	I care about the success of brands that use AI-generated content on social media (Instagram and TikTok).	[11]
Trust	TR1	I believe that the way user data is used in creating social media content (Instagram and TikTok) affects my level of trust in the brand	[36]
	TR2	I feel that AI-generated content is reliable, as brands will not spread digital footprints on social media (Instagram and TikTok) after I view the content presented.	[36]
	TR3	I trust social media content (Instagram and TikTok) created with the help of AI-generated tools	[9]
Information Quality	IQ1	I believe the information on social media content (TikTok and Instagram) created using AI-generated tools is accurate	[38]
	IQ2	I believe the information on social media content (TikTok and Instagram) created using AI-generated tools is reliable.	[26]
	IQ3	I believe the information on social media content (TikTok and Instagram) created using AI-generated tools is relevant.	[38]
Hedonic Motivation	HM1	Watching various content created using AI-generated tools on social media (TikTok and Instagram) excites me.	[45]
	HM2	I watch various AI-generated content on social media (TikTok and Instagram) to spend enjoyable leisure time.	[26]
	HM3	I find pleasure in browsing various AI-generated content on social media (TikTok and Instagram) for shopping	[26]
Positive Emotion	PE1	Seeing various AI generated content displayed on social media (TikTok and Instagram) makes me feel more relaxed.	[46]
	PE2	I feel that the AI generated content displayed on social media (TikTok and Instagram) funny.	[46]
	PE3	I find AI generated content featured on social media (TikTok and Instagram) entertaining.	[46]
Satisfaction	SA1	I feel that the AI-generated content on social media (TikTok and Instagram) meets my expectations.	[47]

Variables	Indicators		Sources
	SA2	I am satisfied with the AI-generated content on social media (TikTok and Instagram).	[30]
	SA3	I believe the AI-generated content on social media (TikTok and Instagram) makes me want to recommend it to others.	[47]
Social Interaction	SI1	With AI-generated content, I can interact with people who share similar interests through social media (TikTok and Instagram).	[26]
	SI2	Interacting with others on AI-generated content through social media (TikTok and Instagram) makes me happy	[26]
	SI3	With AI-generated content, I can meet new people who share similar interests through social media (TikTok and Instagram).	[26]
Customer Engagement	UE1	I watch and view various AI-generated content on social media (TikTok and Instagram)	[48]
	UE2	I would recommend various products and services created using AI on social media (TikTok and Instagram)	[48]
	UE3	actively interact (watch, comment, like, or share content) with brands that use AI-generated content on social media (TikTok and Instagram).	[49]

3.2 Research Population and Sampling Design

The respondents in this study refer to social media users in the DKI Jakarta area who have made purchases of products marketed through social media (TikTok and Instagram) where the marketing content displayed was AI-generated content. The reason why the focus of research was carried out in DKI Jakarta areas because it has high number of social media user. In 2022, social media in this area reached 70.35% of the total population. The minimum sample of this study was calculated using Slovin's formula. The calculation can be seen below.

Slovin formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

n = sample size
N = population size
e² = margin of error

Minimum sample calculation:

$$n = \frac{7,459,918}{1 + 7,459,918 (0,5^2)}$$

n = 399,99
n = 400

Based on calculation above it can be conclude that if the minimum number of sampels is 400 respondents. A total of 502 responses were collected, with 453 valid responses after eliminating bias and misaligned data.

The present research employs a quantitative approach with an explanatory survey design, with the objective of testing the causal relationship between variables based on an existing theoretical framework. The rationale behind the selection of this design is its capacity to facilitate empirical hypothesis testing through the utilization of primary data obtained from questionnaires. The present research adopts an approach that has been utilized in previous studies, who examined customer engagement in various global industries using the meta-analysis method [9], and other studies that used PLS-SEM to examine consumer behaviour in e-commerce in Malaysia [26]. Furthermore, other studies conducted in China utilised an explanatory design to analyze the influence of AIGC on psychological engagement and customer behavior [29]. This comparison demonstrates that the quantitative approach and the utilization of PLS-SEM models have become pertinent and efficacious methodologies in the context of studies across

regions and industry sectors. This lends support to the validity of the approach in this study.

A review of the extant literature indicates that, despite the growing utilization of AI-generated content (AIGC) in digital marketing, there remains a degree of uncertainty surrounding its efficacy in enhancing customer engagement on social media, particularly within the Indonesian context. The majority of extant studies have focused on users' perceptions or attitudes towards AIGC in a global context that can explain the relationship between AIGC and customer engagement. It is evident that further research is required to establish empirical evidence regarding the manner in which factors such as trust, commitment, information quality, satisfaction, positive emotion, social interaction, and hedonic motivation interact within the context of AIGC on social media platforms such as TikTok and Instagram.

The present study diverges from previous research in several significant ways. Firstly, in contrast to studies such as [29], [33] which focus more on user perceptions of AIGC in general or conduct limited experiments, this study uses a quantitative approach based on a conceptual model that integrates psychological variables such as trust, satisfaction, commitment, and positive emotion in

the context of using AIGC. Secondly, the present study was conducted in the DKI Jakarta area, which is representative of an active digital market in Indonesia that has not been specifically studied in the global literature. Thirdly, the study under discussion places particular emphasis on two primary platforms, namely TikTok and Instagram, and employs empirical measurement to ascertain the impact of AIGC on both platforms, with regard to customer engagement. It is noteworthy that this specific aspect has hitherto received scant attention in the wider academic literature, which has instead adopted a more general approach to the subject. Consequently, this study offers a novel contribution to the local and empirical understanding of the effectiveness of AIGC in increasing customer engagement on social media.

4. RESULT

4.1 Responden Demographic

The data used in this study based on an online questionnaire prepared based on the statement of research variables in table 2. For the sampling method, purposive sampling is used because this study has certain consideration in sampling for certain purposed. The responden demographic can be seen at tabel 3.

Tabel 3: responden demographic

No	Demographics	Category	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Gender	Man	189	37.6%
		Woman	313	62.4%
2.	Age	< 21	89	17.7%
		21 – 30	266	53%
		30 – 39	103	20.5%
		> 39	44	8.8%
3.	Domicile	South Jakarta	135	26.9%
		East Jakarta	113	22.5%
		Central Jakarta	89	17.7%
		West Jakarta	111	22.1%
		North Jakarta	54	10.8%
4.	Have made purchases of products marketed through social media (TikTok and Instagram) where the marketing content displayed was AI-generated content.	Yes	494	98.4%

A total of 502 responses were collected from the distributed survey. After eliminating bias (removing 41 responses) and ensuring alignment

with the scope of the research (removing 8 responses), the final valid dataset for processing and analysis in this research consists of 453 respondents.

This dataset meets the minimum requirement of 400 respondents.

4.2 Evaluation Model

Partial Least Squares (PLS) analysis, conducted using SmartPLS, the results of these calculations are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. PLS Result

4.2.1 Outer Model

4.2.1.1 Convergent Validity

Convergent validity is assessed by looking at the loading factor. Variables are said to be valid if the loading factor is above 0.7 [50]. The convergent validity result can be seen in table 4

Tabel 4: Convergent validity result

Indicator Code	Loading Factor Score
<i>Commitment</i>	
CM1	0.804
CM2	0.725
CM3	0.772
CM4	0.792
<i>Trust</i>	
TR1	0.750
TR2	0.825
TR3	0.831
<i>Information Quality</i>	

IQ1	0.816
IQ2	0.794
IQ3	0.813
<i>Hedonic Motivation</i>	
HM1	0.814
HM2	0.833
HM3	0.816
<i>Positive Emotion</i>	
PE1	0.796
PE2	0.820
PE3	0.807
<i>Satisfaction</i>	
SA1	0.803
SA2	0.832
SA3	0.797
<i>Social Interaction</i>	
SI1	0.808
SI2	0.838
SI3	0.803
<i>Customer Engagement</i>	
CE1	0.785
CE2	0.818
CE3	0.829

In Table 4, it can be observed that all indicators for the variable's commitment, trust, information quality, hedonic motivation, positive emotion, user satisfaction, social interaction, and customer engagement have values exceeding 0.70. Therefore, it can be concluded that all indicators have successfully reflected their respective latent variables.

4.2.1.2 Discriminant Validity

discriminant validity will be assessed based on cross-loading. The criterion for conducting discriminant validity is that the indicator values for each construct should be higher than those for other constructs [50].

Tabel 5: Cross-loading result

	Commitment	Customer Engagement	Hedonic Motivation	Information Quality	Positive Emotion	Satisfaction	Social Interaction	Trust
CE1	0.565	0.785	0.608	0.443	0.552	0.592	0.555	0.460
CE2	0.654	0.818	0.622	0.572	0.581	0.644	0.633	0.546
CE3	0.625	0.829	0.614	0.585	0.557	0.591	0.626	0.515
CM1	0.804	0.578	0.590	0.557	0.595	0.581	0.548	0.566
CM2	0.725	0.548	0.462	0.508	0.477	0.526	0.467	0.525
CM3	0.772	0.608	0.595	0.493	0.538	0.582	0.541	0.515

CM4	0.792	0.616	0.618	0.572	0.557	0.575	0.559	0.576
HM1	0.621	0.614	0.814	0.551	0.578	0.568	0.560	0.513
HM2	0.623	0.618	0.833	0.564	0.605	0.619	0.614	0.552
HM3	0.567	0.634	0.816	0.591	0.651	0.678	0.649	0.561
IQ1	0.570	0.487	0.556	0.816	0.536	0.558	0.513	0.609
IQ2	0.545	0.570	0.546	0.794	0.555	0.555	0.535	0.613
IQ3	0.554	0.542	0.576	0.813	0.588	0.592	0.584	0.586
PE1	0.528	0.539	0.587	0.521	0.796	0.563	0.532	0.500
PE2	0.669	0.622	0.644	0.628	0.820	0.625	0.621	0.586
PE3	0.482	0.509	0.566	0.517	0.807	0.559	0.528	0.494
SA1	0.619	0.589	0.645	0.622	0.605	0.850	0.598	0.582
SA2	0.571	0.604	0.598	0.553	0.582	0.794	0.569	0.586
SA3	0.587	0.633	0.596	0.535	0.571	0.784	0.601	0.504
SI1	0.551	0.571	0.629	0.555	0.579	0.590	0.803	0.508
SI2	0.607	0.656	0.640	0.569	0.617	0.606	0.832	0.561
SI3	0.503	0.584	0.529	0.515	0.499	0.575	0.797	0.468
TR1	0.508	0.445	0.481	0.484	0.431	0.474	0.443	0.750
TR2	0.573	0.551	0.527	0.663	0.558	0.607	0.545	0.825
TR3	0.611	0.505	0.579	0.630	0.579	0.567	0.529	0.831

In Table 5 above, it can be seen that each indicator in the constructs has a higher value compared to other constructs. This indicates that each indicator is distinct and contributes to the model, making the indicators valid based on the results of the discriminant validity test using cross-loading values. In addition to cross-loading values, discriminant validity can also be measured using the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) test. This test is used to evaluate the accuracy of a measurement tool by examining the variance of each indicator within the construct. The criterion for AVE measurement is that the AVE value must exceed 0.5.

Tabel 6: Average Variance Extracted Result

Variables	AVE
Commitment	0.599
Customer Engagement	0.658
Hedonic Motivation	0.674
Information Quality	0.653
Positive Emotion	0.652
Satisfaction	0.656
Social Interaction	0.657
Trust	0.645

From the tabel 6 above, it can be seen that all variables used have an Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value greater than 0.50. Therefore, it can be concluded that all variables are valid and suitable for use.

4.2.1.3 Composite Reliability

Composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha are used to measure the reliability of the constructs in reflecting the variables. A variable is considered consistent and reliable if the Cronbach's alpha value is greater than 0.7 and the composite reliability value is greater than 0.7 [51].

Tabel 7: Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha Result

Variabel	Nilai Composite reliability	Cronbach's Alpha
Commitment	0.856	0.776
Customer Engagement	0.852	0.740
Hedonic Motivation	0.861	0.759

Information Quality	0.849	0.734
Positive Emotion	0.849	0.736
Satisfaction	0.851	0.736
Social Interaction	0.852	0.740
Trust	0.845	0.726

Based on the results in table 7, it can be seen that the composite reliability and cronbach's alpha values for all constructs meet the required criteria, where all values are above 0.70. Therefore, all constructs demonstrate good reliability.

4.2.2 Inner Model

4.2.2.1 R-Square

R-Square is used to determine the ability of the independent variable to explain the dependent variable. R-Square value can be said to be moderate if it has a value between 0.05 – 0.075 and if the value is greater than 0.75, it has strong influence in predicting independent variables [50].

Tabel 8: R-Square Result

Variabel	R Square (R ²)	Kriteria
Customer Engagement	0,687	Moderat
Positive Emotion	0,546	Moderat
Satisfaction	0,625	Moderat

Based on the output in tabel 8, it can be seen that the R-Square value for customer engagement is 0.687, which mean that the customer engagement variable can be explained by the hedonic motivation, positive emotion, satisfaction, and social interaction variables by 68.7%. Meanwhile, 31.3% is explained by variables outside this study, which illustrated that variables used have a moderate correlation.

While positive emotion has a value of 0.546, which means that the positive emotion variable can be explained by commitment and trust by 54.6% and 45.4% by variable outside this study, which illustrates that the variables used have a moderate correlation.

Furthermore, the satisfaction variable has a value of 0.625, which means that the satisfaction variable explained by commitment, trust, information quality by 62.5% while the 37.5% explained by variable outside this study, which

illustrates that the variables used have a moderate correlation.

4.2.2.2 Q-Square

The Q-Square test is performed to see the predictive relevance. Predictive relevance is done using a blindfolding procedure that can show the value > 0, it can be concluded that the observation value has a good value. Meanwhile, if the Q-Square value < 0 then the observation value has a poor value [52].

Tabel 9: Q-Square Result

Variabel	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Commitment	1.812.000	1.210.003	0.332
Customer Engagement	1.359.000	931.245	0.315
Hedonic Motivation	1.359.000	890.979	0.344
Information Quality	1.359.000	941.137	0.307
Positive Emotion	1.359.000	943.755	0.306
Satisfaction	1.359.000	933.197	0.313
Social Interaction	1.359.000	934.286	0.313
Trust	1.359.000	955.474	0.297

Based on Q-Square test relust in tabel 9, it can be seen that all variables have an observation value > 0, so that all variables have good predictive relevance.

4.2.3 Path Coefficient and Hypothesis Result

The calculations are performed using the bootstrapping procedure in SmartPLS. The results of the bootstrapping calculations are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Bootstrapping Result

Calculation results as can be seen below.

Tabel 10: Path Coefficient

Hypothesis	Path Coefficient
Commitment -> Positive Emotion	0.476
Commitment -> Satisfaction	0.397
Trust -> Positive Emotion	0.322
Trust -> Satisfaction	0.198
Information Quality -> Satisfaction	0.284
Hedonic Motivation -> Customer Engagement	0.271
Positive Emotion -> Customer Engagement	0.104
Satisfaction -> Customer Engagement	0.269
Social Interaction -> Customer Engagement	0.277

From the results in table 10, it can be observed that the path coefficient values for the direct effect are above 0 and close to 1. This indicates that all relationships between variables in this study have a positive correlation.

Tabel 11: Hypothesis Test Result

Hypothesis	T-Statistic	P-Values	Result
H1 Commitment -> Positive Emotion	8.663	0.000	accepted
H2 Commitment -> Satisfaction	7.271	0.000	accepted
H3 Trust -> Positive Emotion	5.758	0.000	accepted
H4 Trust -> Satisfaction	3.586	0.000	accepted
H5 Information Quality -> Satisfaction	5.159	0.000	accepted
H6 Hedonic Motivation -> Customer Engagement	4.045	0.000	accepted
H7 Positive Emotion -> Customer Engagement	1.979	0.048	accepted
H8 Satisfaction -> Customer Engagement	4.561	0.000	accepted
H9 Social Interaction -> Customer Engagement	5.096	0.000	accepted

Based on the data analysis results in table 11, the hypothesis analysis can be described as follows:

[H1] Commitment has a significant effect on Positive Emotion in AIGC on social media.

With a path coefficient of 0.476, T-Statistic of 8.663, and p-value of 0.000, H1 is accepted. Customers who feel committed to brands using AIGC experience increased positive emotions. This research shows that the increased willingness of customers to stay connected, interact, and care for brands using AIGC can evoke positive emotion. This is due to the content displayed through AIGC on social media platforms like TikTok and Instagram able to entertains and provides a relaxing feeling. This relationship is formed because the psychological condition that triggers commitment to a brand also triggers positive emotion [11].

Therefore, the use of AI-generated content (AIGC) for creating social media content is highly recommended, given its ability to produce content that aligns with customer preferences. This allows businesses to reduce concerns regarding content

alignment with their brand and target audience. Such an approach can help address the issue of low engagement on social media platforms, particularly TikTok and Instagram, which is often caused by content irrelevance to customers' interests and needs.

[H2] Commitment has a significant effect on Satisfaction in AIGC on social media.

With a path coefficient of 0.397, T-Statistic of 7.271, and p-value of 0.000, H2 is accepted. An increase in commitment when viewing AIGC offered by brands on social media will add value to satisfaction. The research shows that customer's willingness to maintain sustainable relationships with brands using AIGC will contribute to overall satisfaction and increase customers' desire to recommend products or services on social media, whereas TikTok and Instagram. The significant effect is consistent with previous research, where the willingness of customers to maintain long-term relationships and continue to interact with a brand gives satisfaction [9].

By generating content that is both relevant and tailored to audience preferences, businesses are better positioned to foster long-term relationships founded on meaningful interaction and perceived care. This approach not only contributes to increased overall customer satisfaction but also stimulates positive word-of-mouth, particularly on dynamic platforms such as TikTok and Instagram. Consequently, AI-generated content (AIGC)-driven marketing strategies can be strategically leveraged to enhance customer loyalty and deepen engagement.

[H3] Trust has a significant effect on Positive Emotion in AIGC on social media.

With a 0.322 path coefficient, a 5.758 T-Statistic, and a p-value of 0.000, so H3 is accepted. The development of trust in AIGC from brands enhances customers' positive emotions, is confidence in content creation fosters positive expectations. Trust in both the process and the content helps customers feel more relaxed in AIGC. However, the finding is different from previous research, that trust does not directly affect positive emotion. This discrepancy develops because positive emotion is inherently independent and requires companies to ensure that every customer interaction remains enjoyable to sustain engagement and satisfaction [9].

To evoke positive emotions, such as feelings of entertainment, relaxation, and trust toward the presented content, businesses that utilizing AI-generated content (AIGC) must carefully consider the extent to which customer data is used in the content creation process. This is essential to ensure that all produced content remains ethical and does not violate customer privacy. The use of customer data without explicit consent should be strictly avoided to maintain the trustworthiness of the content. By creating transparent and ethically sound content, businesses can strengthen emotional connections with customers on social media platforms.

[H4] Trust has a significant effect on Satisfaction in AIGC on social media.

With a 0.198 path coefficient, a 3.586T statistic, and a 0.000 p-value, so H4 is accepted. The trust experienced develop when viewing AIGC displayed by brands on social media adds value to satisfaction. The trust not only boosts satisfaction but also encourages customers to recommend products or services. It is aligned with previous research, where trust significantly influences satisfaction. Companies must prioritize developing trust to increase engagement, as confidence in the

technology used fosters satisfaction. When customers trust AIGC, so they are more likely to feel satisfied [9], [53].

Although customers may be aware that their data is utilized in the creation of AI-generated content (AIGC), businesses must still ensure transparency in its use, given that many customers remain uncertain about the extent to which their data is being leveraged. By fostering strong trust, businesses can expand their market reach, as customers who feel confident in a brand are more likely to recommend its products or services to others.

[H5] Information Quality has a significant effect on Satisfaction in AIGC on Social Media

With a 0.284 path coefficient, a 5.159 T-Statistic, and a 0.000 p-value, H5 is accepted. High-quality AIGC such accurate, relevant, and reliable and able to enhance satisfaction. The significant effect between information quality and satisfaction is supported by previous research [26], [38] satisfaction. The research showed that social media success heavily depends on the quality of the information provided; if the information provided is inconsistent, customers will not derive value from the information, leading to a decrease in customer satisfaction.

The use of AI-generated content (AIGC), which can produce accurate, relevant, and reliable content, helps ensure that customer expectations are met and provides satisfaction when engaging with social media content. This allows businesses to alleviate concerns regarding unclear or insufficient information delivery. However, to maintain the appeal of the content, businesses using AIGC must ensure that the input keywords are appropriate, specific, and unambiguous so that the information provided offers added value, such as being useful and accurate, thereby supporting informed decision-making.

[H6] Hedonic Motivation has a significant effect on Customer Engagement in AIGC on Social Media

With a 0.271 path coefficient, a 4.045T-Statistic, and a 0.000 p-value, so H6 is accepted. Enjoyment and enthusiasm from viewing AIGC encourage active engagement, especially on platforms like TikTok and Instagram. When customers find content entertaining, they interact more, leading to increased engagement. In line with previous studies, where satisfaction drives customer participation [40]. Customer engagement on social media is based on the pleasure and enjoyment

experienced. The customers feel their emotional needs are met and enjoy the experience, which will encourage positive attitudes, such as more frequent visits and repeat purchases [26].

Based on this study, it is found that AI-generated content (AIGC) can enhance hedonic motivation by providing content accompanied by visuals that attract customers' attention and offer enjoyment, whether simply to pass leisure time or to shop through social media platforms, particularly TikTok and Instagram. Consequently, the pleasure and excitement experienced by customers when viewing various AIGC encourage them to actively interact with the content, especially on TikTok and Instagram, ultimately fostering customer engagement.

[H7] Positive Emotion has a significant effect on Customer Engagement in AIGC on Social Media

With a 0.104 path coefficient, 1.979 T-Statistic, and 0.048 p-value, sp H7 is accepted. AIGC on social media platforms such as TikTok and Instagram engage positive feelings and encourage active engagement. Entertaining and relaxing content aligns with customers' humor and fosters interaction, in line with the prior study, where the increase in positive emotions develop the likelihood of customers interacting, which leads to engagement. Therefore, companies have to ensure every interaction is according on a pleasant experience [9], [29].

By creating entertaining content that aligns with customers' sense of humor, AI-generated content (AIGC) can help prevent customer boredom caused by monotonous social media marketing content. The ease of producing diverse content ideas and themes based on given keywords enables businesses to create various product descriptions, images, and marketing videos. Moreover, the support in generating entertaining content tailored to customers' humor preferences encourages active customer interaction, which in turn enhances customer engagement.

[H8] Satisfaction has a significant effect on Customer Engagement in AIGC on Social Media

With a 0.269 path coefficient, 4.561 T-Statistic, and 0.000p-value, so H8 is accepted. Higher customer satisfaction leads in developing engagement, such as satisfied customers are more likely to interact actively. AIGC is essential to enhance engagement fulfill customer expectations and provide enjoyable content. When customers feel satisfied, they are motivated to recommend products or services, which leads to more frequent

interactions. It aligns with previous research [9], [19], where satisfaction significantly impacts engagement in social media.

In this context, the use of AI-generated content (AIGC) can be an effective strategy for businesses to enhance customer engagement. This is driven by the feelings of satisfaction, fulfillment of expectations, and the willingness of customers to recommend products or services to others when exposed to AIGC, which directly stimulates active interaction and ultimately increases customer engagement. Therefore, it can be concluded that the use of AIGC has been proven capable of fulfilling customer satisfaction, which helps prevent the decline of interaction on social media and addresses the decrease in customer engagement.

[H9] Social Interaction has a significant effect on Customer Engagement in AIGC on Social Media

With a 0.277 path coefficient, 5.096 T-Statistic, and 0.000 p-value, so H8 is accepted. AIGC facilitates customer connections and fosters positive engagement on social media. Social interaction development enhances engagement, where customers rely on social platforms to interact with others and make purchasing decisions. In line with [26], where higher social interaction leads to greater engagement. Additionally, interactive dialogues give valuable insights for brand to refine content strategies and develop customer engagement [19], [42]. Thus, engaging meaningful social interactions through AIGC can drive stronger engagement.

Given the interactive nature of social media, the ease with which AI-generated content (AIGC) can respond to the market more quickly helps ensure that interactions on social media remain active. Sustained interaction increases activity on social media and fosters joyful exchanges among customers, which ultimately contributes to enhanced customer engagement.

5. CONCLUSIONS

5.1 Overall Interpretation

After conducting the research on "The Influence of AI-Generated Content in Enhancing Customer Engagement on Social Media" using the Partial Least Square (PLS) method with SmartPLS 4 software, this study utilized 453 valid datasets. The respondents were residents of DKI Jakarta who had purchased products marketed through social media (TikTok and Instagram) using AI-generated content. The reearch found that the strategic use of AIGC enhances social media's effectiveness in supporting marketing activities.

The findings show that all proposed hypotheses were accepted, with the following results: Commitment significantly influences positive emotion in AIGC on social media, with a T-Statistic of 8.663 and a P-Value of 0.000. Commitment also significantly influences satisfaction, with a T-Statistic of 7.271 and a P-Value of 0.000. Trust significantly influences positive emotion, with a T-Statistic of 5.758 and a P-Value of 0.000, and satisfaction, with a T-Statistic of 3.586 and a P-Value of 0.000. Information quality significantly influences satisfaction, with a T-Statistic of 5.159 and a P-Value of 0.000. Hedonic motivation significantly influences customer engagement, with a T-Statistic of 4.045 and a P-Value of 0.000. Positive emotion significantly influences customer engagement, with a T-Statistic of 1.979 and a P-Value of 0.048. Satisfaction significantly influences customer engagement, with a T-Statistic of 4.561 and a P-Value of 0.000. Social interaction significantly influences customer engagement, with a T-Statistic of 5.096 and a P-Value of 0.000.

The research indicates that AI-generated content (AIGC) enhances customer engagement. Brand should not only utilize AIGC but optimize it, focusing on factors that drive engagement, particularly social interaction. AIGC allows businesses to create content quickly while aligning with customer preferences, maintaining interactive dialogue, and enhancing social media experiences. Another key factor is hedonic motivation, as unappealing content can hinder engagement. Brand can leverage AIGC to improve visual quality and incorporate entertainment and creativity.

This research makes a significant scientific contribution to the realm of digital marketing, especially in the utilization of AI Generated Content (AIGC) in increasing customer engagement on social media. In contrast to previous studies that have focused on general perceptions of AIGC globally [29], [33], this study builds and tests a conceptual model based on psychological variables such as trust, satisfaction, commitment, and positive emotion in the context of Indonesian users. The present study also focuses on two dominant platforms, TikTok and Instagram, which have rarely been the focus of empirical literature. Furthermore, the utilisation of a PLS-SEM-based quantitative approach facilitates a more precise estimation of the relative contribution of each factor to customer engagement. Consequently, this study enhances the

existing literature on AIGC by offering localized and applicable empirical insights for emerging markets.

Although positive emotion influences engagement, its impact is lower than satisfaction. While AIGC on TikTok and Instagram helps prevent boredom, customer responses to its ability to provide relaxation and humor are moderate. As a result, positive emotion is not an effective intervening variable for commitment and trust. Businesses should instead focus on satisfaction. To enhance satisfaction, businesses should prioritize strengthening commitment by aligning content with customer preferences, followed by ensuring high-quality content. Building trust is also crucial, considering concerns about data usage and potential bias in AIGC. This approach will improve the customer experience by fulfilling expectations and increasing satisfaction.

The findings of this study successfully achieved the initial objective, which was to identify and measure the influence of factors such as commitment, trust, satisfaction, and others on customer engagement through AI-generated content. Empirical evidence has demonstrated the significance of all proposed hypotheses, thereby indicating that AIGC possesses considerable potential in enhancing customer engagement on social media platforms. This finding is consistent with the conclusions of recent studies [9], [29], [33], which emphasise the role of AIGC in facilitating a more personalized and efficient customer engagement. However, in contrast to studies that address issues of ethics and content authenticity [23], this study has not examined these negative impacts directly. Consequently, it is proposed that subsequent research should encompass components of users' perceptions of the credibility and originality of AI content, and extend the sample coverage beyond Jakarta to enhance the generalizability of the results.

The findings of this study successfully address the two main research objectives: identifying the factors that influence the use of AI-generated content (AIGC) on social media in relation to customer engagement and assessing their impact. Analysis using PLS-SEM revealed that commitment, trust, satisfaction, information quality, hedonic motivation, positive emotion, and social interaction all significantly influence customer engagement. Satisfaction and social interaction emerged as the most influential factors, while positive emotion had a relatively lower impact and

was less effective as a mediating variable between commitment/trust and engagement. These results highlight the strategic value of AIGC in enhancing customer engagement on platforms like TikTok and Instagram. Therefore, businesses should optimize customer satisfaction by aligning content with user preferences, ensuring content quality, and establishing credibility. This study also contributes meaningfully to the digital marketing literature by providing localized empirical insights into the role of AIGC in emerging markets, contrasting with previous global-focused studies.

5.2 Implications

The study highlights the crucial role of AI-generated content (AIGC) in enhancing customer engagement on social media, such as TikTok and Instagram. AIGC enables brands to create content related to customer preferences. Brands must focus on producing relevant content and fostering long-term, interactive relationships with customers. AIGC effectively aims to lower engagement by generating content that matches customer interests and needs.

Commitment plays a key role in increasing satisfaction using AIGC on social media. When customers feel committed to brands using AIGC, their satisfaction rises, leading to stronger brand relationships. Brands can leverage AIGC to create content which related to customer preferences, fostering loyalty and engagement. Interactive AIGC-based marketing strategies encourage customers to recommend products or services, mostly on TikTok and Instagram.

Trust significantly impacts positive emotions and satisfaction in AIGC on social media. Customers who trust AIGC experience greater satisfaction. The brand should ensure AIGC is managed ethically, as trustworthy content strengthens emotional connections and develops recommendations. The trust manage in AIGC information carefully helps meet customer expectations and enhances brand perception.

Information quality plays an essential role in customer satisfaction with AIGC. Accurate, relevant, and reliable content fulfills customer expectations, also enhances satisfaction. The brand should optimize AIGC inputs by using appropriate and specific keywords. High-quality information adds value, aids decision-making, and develops engagement. To ensure AIGC produces informative content helps brands maintain audience interest and satisfaction.

Hedonic motivation is a key engagement driver with AIGC. Customers who enjoy and find AIGC content entertaining are more likely to engage. A major barrier to engagement is not appealing content, like poor visuals or low-quality editing. AIGC helps overcome it by producing visually appealing and engaging content, especially on TikTok and Instagram. Exciting and entertaining content encourages active participation and boosts engagement.

Positive emotions enhance customer engagement with AIGC. Brands should use AIGC to create humorous and entertaining content that aligns with customer preferences and prevents boredom. AIGC's ability to generate diverse themes and creative ideas helps brands produce dynamic product descriptions, images, and marketing videos. Engaging and interactive content develops active customer interaction and increases engagement.

Customer satisfaction is crucial to driving engagement with AIGC. When satisfied, customers are more likely to engage and recommend products or services. AIGC helps brands sustain engagement to fulfill customer satisfaction and prevent disengagement. It also helps counteract decreased social media engagement with relevant and high-quality content.

Social interaction enhances significantly engagement with AIGC. The interaction increased while viewing AIGC content fosters engagement and makes it crucial for brands to align marketing strategies with customer interests. The speed and adaptability of AI-assisted content creation help brands stay relevant to trends and ensure continuous engagement. AIGC's ability to adjust to market changes encourages enjoyable social interactions, driving higher activity and engagement.

The research found a positive emotion is not the primary mediator among commitment and trust in AIGC-driven engagement. While customers committed to brands using AIGC may have positive emotions and trust, positive emotions do not drive direct engagement. However, commitment and trust still play a direct role in customer engagement. To address this, brand using AIGC for social media marketing should carefully curate content ideas to keep customers engaged. Rather than focusing solely on positive emotions, businesses should prioritize creating content that meets customer expectations and satisfaction. Reliable AIGC-generated content

enhances satisfaction and encourages active engagement.

5.3 Limitation and Future Work

The main purpose of this research is to explore the use of AIGC, especially in creating content on social media, considering the many obstacles felt by business in the process of creating content that suits their customers. However, this research is not free from shortcomings, some of the main limitations that arise in this research are the scope of the research implementation. First, the scope is too focused on customer behavior and perceptions, such as commitment, trust, satisfaction, positive emotion, social influence, and hedonic motivation. This in-depth focus on psychological and social aspects led to the neglect of technology, models, and training parameters that can also affect the final quality of the resulting AIGC.

Whilst the present study contributes to the understanding of the influence of using AI Generated Content (AIGC) on customer engagement, there are several open issues that require further study. The present study is confined to the DKI Jakarta area; consequently, the results obtained should be generalized with caution, as they may not be representative of national or global populations. Furthermore, the present study did not directly explore user perceptions of the authenticity and credibility of AI-generated content, which, in other studies, have been shown to influence user engagement [23]. The study was also cross-sectional in nature, which precluded the observation of changes in engagement over time. Moreover, the study did not undertake a direct comparison of human-generated content with AI-generated content, nor a combination of both. Further exploration is required into other aspects, including but not limited to the ethical use of data, the issue of over-personalization, and the phenomenon of trust fatigue resulting from the use of AI. Consequently, future research is expected to extend the geographical and thematic scope, and to employ longitudinal and mixed-method approaches, with a view to generating a more comprehensive understanding.

In addition, this study only touched on the potential and basic characteristics of AIGC and user responses, so it has not fully explored how variations in content such as text, photos, and videos can influence preferences and engagement, especially in different industry contexts. Therefore, future research is expected to expand the scope of the study by

integrating the analysis results of the systems used in AI technologies used in content creation. This interdisciplinary approach allows for a more in-depth mapping. Thus, this understanding can open up opportunities in the development of a more adaptive AIGC system.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Pusparisa, "Lima Alasan Pemasaran Merek Dagang Memanfaatkan Media Sosial," Databoks. Accessed: Jul. 20, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://databoks.katadata.co.id/datapublish/2020/12/09/lima-alasan-pemasaran-merek-dagang-memanfaatkan-media-sosial>
- [2] Score, "Infographic: Small Business Social Media Trends," Score. Accessed: Jul. 20, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.score.org/resource/infographic/infographic-how-your-small-business-can-succeed-social-media>
- [3] G. Ali Abbasi, N. F. Abdul Rahim, H. Wu, M. Iranmanesh, and B. N. C. Keong, "Determinants of SME's Social Media Marketing Adoption: Competitive Industry as a Moderator," *Sage Open*, vol. 12, no. 1, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1177/21582440211067220/ASSET/IMAGES/LARGE/10.1177_21582440211067220-FIG4.JPEG.
- [4] X. Fan, "Social Media Marketing Strategies," *Advances in Economics, Management and Political Sciences*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 59–64, Sep. 2023, doi: 10.54254/2754-1169/23/20230353.
- [5] Z. Wang, "Social media brand posts and customer engagement," *Journal of Brand Management*, vol. 28, no. 6, pp. 685–699, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.1057/S41262-021-00247-5/METRICS.
- [6] M. Yuen, "Most B2B content marketers have trouble creating the right content for their audience," eMarketer. Accessed: Jul. 20, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.emarketer.com/content/most-b2b-content-marketers-have-trouble-creating-right-content-their-audience>
- [7] Statista, "Worldwide: how brands fail to engage with customers 2023 | Statista," Statista. Accessed: May 04, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1425554/brands-fail-to-engage-with-customers/>

- [8] J. Haws, "The social media benchmarks to guide your 2024 strategy," *emplifi*. Accessed: May 04, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://emplifi.io/resources/blog/social-media-benchmarks>
- [9] F. de O. Santini, W. J. Ladeira, D. C. Pinto, M. M. Herter, C. H. Sampaio, and B. J. Babin, "Customer engagement in social media: a framework and meta-analysis," *J Acad Mark Sci*, vol. 48, no. 6, pp. 1211–1228, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1007/S11747-020-00731-5/TABLES/6.
- [10] A. Matin, T. Khoshtaria, and G. Tutberidze, "The impact of social media engagement on consumers' trust and purchase intention," *International Journal of Technology Marketing*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 305–323, 2020, doi: 10.1504/IJTMKT.2020.111547.
- [11] S. Vinerean and A. Opreana, "Measuring Customer Engagement in Social Media Marketing: A Higher-Order Model," *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research 2021, Vol. 16, Pages 2633-2654*, vol. 16, no. 7, pp. 2633–2654, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.3390/JTAER16070145.
- [12] B. A. Apenteng, I. B. Ekpo, F. M. Mutiso, E. A. Akowuah, and S. T. Opoku, "Examining the relationship between social media engagement and hospital revenue," *Health Mark Q*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 10–21, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1080/07359683.2020.1713575.
- [13] H. Pallathadka, E. H. Ramirez-Asis, T. P. Loli-Poma, K. Kaliyaperumal, R. J. M. Ventayen, and M. Naved, "Applications of artificial intelligence in business management, e-commerce and finance," *Mater Today Proc*, vol. 80, pp. 2610–2613, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1016/J.MATPR.2021.06.419.
- [14] H. Du *et al.*, "Enabling AI-Generated Content (AIGC) Services in Wireless Edge Networks," *IEEE Wirel Commun*, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1109/MWC.004.2300015.
- [15] Hootsuite, "74 Artificial Intelligence Statistics to Guide Your Marketing Plan," Hootsuite. Accessed: May 04, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://blog.hootsuite.com/artificial-intelligence-statistics/#Artificial_intelligence_customer_service_statistics
- [16] S. Arshad, "PERFORMANCE OF AI GENERATED CONTENT IN CONTENT MARKETING," *Talling University of Technology School of Business and Governance*, 2023, Accessed: May 06, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://digikogu.taltech.ee/et/Download/10c04466-2d22-433a-a6ee-21b44013bb6b/Tehisintellektiloodudsisutoimivussisuturunduse.pdf>
- [17] eMarketer, "The Power of Generative AI in the Buyer's Journey," eMarketer. Accessed: May 04, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.emarketer.com/content/power-of-generative-ai-buyers-journey>
- [18] C. Burlacu, "The Impact of AI-Powered Content Generation on Customer Experience," *Bachelor's thesis, University of Twente*, 2023.
- [19] S. Shawky, K. Kubacki, T. Dietrich, and S. Weaven, "A dynamic framework for managing customer engagement on social media," *J Bus Res*, vol. 121, pp. 567–577, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.JBUSRES.2020.03.030.
- [20] J. Park, C. Oh, and H. Y. Kim, "AI vs. human-generated content and accounts on Instagram: User preferences, evaluations, and ethical considerations," *Technol Soc*, vol. 79, p. 102705, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.1016/J.TECHSOC.2024.102705.
- [21] SMK, "AI Powers 39% of Social Media Marketing Content," Social Media Knowledge. Accessed: Mar. 03, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://smk.co/ai-powers-39-of-social-media-marketing-content/>
- [22] Bynder, "Study reveals how consumers interact with AI-generated content vs human-made," Bynder. Accessed: Mar. 03, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bynder.com/en/press-media/ai-vs-human-made-content-study/>
- [23] J. D. Brüns and M. Meißner, "Do you create your content yourself? Using generative artificial intelligence for social media content creation diminishes perceived brand authenticity," *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, vol. 79, p. 103790, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.1016/J.JRETCONSER.2024.103790.
- [24] S. Chesterman, "AI-Generated Content is Taking over the World. But Who Owns it?," *SSRN Electronic Journal*, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.2139/SSRN.4321596.
- [25] X. J. Lim, J. H. Cheah, D. S. Waller, H. Ting, and S. I. Ng, "What s-commerce implies?"

- Repurchase intention and its antecedents,” *Marketing Intelligence and Planning*, vol. 38, no. 6, pp. 760–776, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1108/MIP-03-2019-0145/FULL/XML.
- [26] A. H. Busalim, F. Ghabban, and A. R. C. Hussin, “Customer engagement behaviour on social commerce platforms: An empirical study,” *Technol Soc*, vol. 64, p. 101437, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.TECHSOC.2020.101437.
- [27] F. Li, J. Larimo, and L. C. Leonidou, “Social media marketing strategy: definition, conceptualization, taxonomy, validation, and future agenda,” *J Acad Mark Sci*, vol. 49, no. 1, pp. 51–70, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1007/S11747-020-00733-3.
- [28] L. Labajová, “The state of AI : Exploring the perceptions, credibility, and trustworthiness of the users towards AI-Generated Content,” 2023, Accessed: May 06, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:mau:diva-61215>
- [29] D. Du, Y. Zhang, and J. Ge, “Effect of AI Generated Content Advertising on Consumer Engagement,” *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, vol. 14039 LNCS, pp. 121–129, 2023, doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-36049-7_9.
- [30] A. Wibowo, S. C. Chen, U. Wiangin, Y. Ma, and A. Ruangkanjanases, “Customer Behavior as an Outcome of Social Media Marketing: The Role of Social Media Marketing Activity and Customer Experience,” *Sustainability 2021, Vol. 13, Page 189*, vol. 13, no. 1, p. 189, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.3390/SU13010189.
- [31] R. Liu, S. Gupta, and P. Patel, “The Application of the Principles of Responsible AI on Social Media Marketing for Digital Health,” *Information Systems Frontiers*, vol. 25, no. 6, pp. 2275–2299, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1007/S10796-021-10191-Z/FIGURES/2.
- [32] K. Bontcheva *et al.*, “Contributing Authors Generative AI and Disinformation: Recent Advances, Challenges, and Opportunities Editor,” *European Digital Media Observatory*, 2024.
- [33] J. Wu, W. Gan, Z. Chen, S. Wan, and H. Lin, “AI-Generated Content (AIGC): A Survey,” no. 304.06632, Mar. 2023, Accessed: Feb. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.06632v1>
- [34] Capgemini, “Generative AI in organizations | Research & insight | Capgemini,” Capgemini. Accessed: May 04, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.capgemini.com/insights/research-library/generative-ai-in-organizations/>
- [35] S. Kelly, S. A. Kaye, and O. Oviedo-Trespalacios, “What factors contribute to the acceptance of artificial intelligence? A systematic review,” *Telematics and Informatics*, vol. 77, p. 101925, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1016/J.TELE.2022.101925.
- [36] S. S. Muhammad, B. L. Dey, M. M. Kamal, and S. F. Syed Alwi, “Consumer engagement with social media platforms: A study of the influence of attitudinal components on cutting edge technology adaptation behaviour,” *Comput Human Behav*, vol. 121, p. 106802, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.CHB.2021.106802.
- [37] C. De Lima, -Claudio Lima@ufsc Br, R. Cid Bastos, L. Caetano Bastos, and -Lia C Bastos@ufsc Br, “The Information Quality impact on Learning Platforms,” *Revista Novas Tecnologias na Educação*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 59–68, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.22456/1679-1916.110204.
- [38] E. M. Safitri, A. Pratama, M. A. Furqon, I. R. Mukhlis, Agussalim, and A. Faroqi, “Interaction effect of system, information and service quality on intention to use and user satisfaction,” *Proceeding - 6th Information Technology International Seminar, ITIS 2020*, pp. 92–97, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1109/ITIS50118.2020.9321002.
- [39] C.-M. Leong, · Alexa, M.-W. Loi, and S. Woon, “The influence of social media eWOM information on purchase intention,” *Journal of Marketing Analytics*, vol. 10, pp. 145–157, 2022, doi: 10.1057/s41270-021-00132-9.
- [40] M. G. Elmashhara, R. De Cicco, S. C. Silva, M. Hammerschmidt, and M. L. Silva, “How gamifying AI shapes customer motivation, engagement, and purchase behavior,” *Psychol Mark*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 134–150, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1002/MAR.21912.
- [41] A. Q. Bataineh, “Analyzing the role of social media marketing in changing customer experience,” *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 761–768, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.5267/J.IJDNS.2022.3.005.
- [42] R. Agnihotri, “Social media, customer engagement, and sales organizations: A

- research agenda,” *Industrial Marketing Management*, vol. 90, pp. 291–299, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.INDMARMAN.2020.07.017.
- [43] I. Kulkov, J. Kulkova, R. Rohrbeck, L. Menvielle, V. Kaartemo, and H. Makkonen, “Artificial intelligence - driven sustainable development: Examining organizational, technical, and processing approaches to achieving global goals,” *Sustainable Development*, 2023, doi: 10.1002/SD.2773.
- [44] S. Ryu and J. K. Park, “The effects of benefit-driven commitment on usage of social media for shopping and positive word-of-mouth,” *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, vol. 55, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jretconser.2020.102094.
- [45] L. Guo, X. Hu, X. Wei, and X. Cai, “The influence of personal motivation and environmental stimuli on customer participation and engagement behavior: the mediating role of experience evaluation,” *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 643–666, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1108/JHTT-02-2020-0043/FULL/XML.
- [46] Z. Lv, W. Zhao, Y. Liu, J. Wu, and M. Hou, “Impact of perceived value, positive emotion, product coolness and Mianzi on new energy vehicle purchase intention,” *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, vol. 76, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.jretconser.2023.103564.
- [47] M. Uzir *et al.*, “Does quality stimulate customer satisfaction where perceived value mediates and the usage of social media moderates?,” *Heliyon*, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e05710.
- [48] T. Wang and F. Y. Lee, “Examining customer engagement and brand intimacy in social media context,” *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, vol. 54, p. 102035, May 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.JRETCONSER.2020.102035.
- [49] A. F. Utami, I. A. Ekaputra, A. Japutra, and S. Van Doorn, “The role of interactivity on customer engagement in mobile e-commerce applications,” <https://doi.org/10.1177/14707853211027483>, vol. 64, no. 2, pp. 269–291, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.1177/14707853211027483.
- [50] L. Yunikartika and Harti, “Pengaruh Social Media Marketing dan Electronic Word Of Mouth (E-WOM) Terhadap Minat Beli Kuliner Melalui Kepercayaan Sebagai Variabel Intervening pada Akun Instagram @carubanmangan,” *Jurnal E-Bis*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 212–230, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.37339/E-BIS.V6I1.897.
- [51] M. I. Nasution, M. Fahmi, Jufrizen, Muslih, and M. A. Prayogi, “The Quality of Small and Medium Enterprises Performance Using the Structural Equation Model-Part Least Square (SEM-PLS),” *Journal of Physics*, 2020, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1477/5/052052.
- [52] M. Karikari Appiah, P. K. Tettevi, N. Amaning, E. Opoku Ware, and C. Kwarteng, “Modeling the implications of internal audit effectiveness on value for money and sustainable procurement performance: An application of structural equation modeling,” *Cogent Business & Management*, vol. 9, no. 1, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1080/23311975.2022.2102127.
- [53] K. H. Seo and J. H. Lee, “The Emergence of Service Robots at Restaurants: Integrating Trust, Perceived Risk, and Satisfaction,” *Sustainability*, vol. 13, no. 8, p. 4431, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.3390/SU13084431.